

Carbon-13 NMR Spectra of Some Benzene Derivatives

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Carbon-13 chemical shifts of some mono-, di- and trioxxygenated benzene derivatives along with the natural products asarylaldehyde and acronylin and its derivative are reported. It was observed that the simple additivity rules were not applicable in tri- and tetrasubstituted benzene derivatives with two or more adjacent oxygen functions.

IN the course of our investigations concerning the synthesis of a few naturally occurring berbenoids, pavinoids, etc., compounds **1-40** having mono-, di- and trioxxygenated benzene rings were derived and their carbon-13 spectra recorded. The carbon shifts are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The shift assignments of acronylin (**43**), a constituent of *Acronychia laurifolia*¹ and its derivative 6-acetyl-5,7-dihydroxy-2,2-dimethylchroman¹ (**44**) are also reported.

We noted during our studies on the carbon-13 nmr spectra of amides², coumarins^{3,4}, chalcones⁵ and phenylpropanes^{6,7} involving polyoxxygenated benzene systems that in many instances ambiguities arose due to large deviation from the additivity rules^{8,9}. The present study was aimed at obtaining some idea of the nature of the deviation observed in simple systems occasionally found as a part of natural molecules.

The effects of introduction of a methoxy substituent on the chemical shifts of the aromatic ring carbons relative to suitable reference compounds are given in Table 3. The observed substituent parameters of a methoxy group differed significantly from the expected values^{8,9} even when there was only one *ortho* substituent to it, but the variation was quite remarkable when the benzene ring incorporated three oxygen and one carbon substituents. Thus, when three oxygen substituents were on contiguous carbons but free from steric interaction with the fourth substituent as in **2, 3, 4, 7** and **9**, the chemical shifts of each of the ring carbons (when compared with those of **22, 23, 24, 25** and **29**, respectively) were largely affected by the presence of the methoxyl at C-5. This led to deshielding of *meta* carbons (C-1 and C-3) and comparatively large change in chemical shift (39.4-42.2 ppm) of the substituted carbon (C-5) in conformity with the out-of-planarity of the methoxyl at C-4 and implying a reduction in electron donating character of the central (C-4) methoxyl function. Furthermore, comparison of the chemical shifts of the aromatic carbons in **13, 14** and **15** (with all the four substituents on contiguous carbons and both methoxyls at C-2 and C-3 out-of-plane of the benzene ring)

with those of **48, 25** and **26**, respectively indicated that the observed *ortho* and *para* substituent effects of the incoming methoxyl (at C-2) were almost half of its normal value (vide Table 3). An examination of Table 3 also revealed that the methoxyl at C-5 in **2, 3, 4, 7** and **9** caused unequal shieldings on the *ortho* carbons viz., -9.2 to -12.4 ppm on C-4 and -14.4 to -17.3 ppm on C-6 (relative to similar carbons in **22, 23, 24, 25** and **29**, respectively). This additional effect on C-6 might be attributable to the strong γ -shielding effect of the O-methyl group¹⁰ at C-5 operating on it. The relatively high shielding of C-2 in **25, 26, 29, 30** and **31** than that of C-4 (compared with similar carbons in **35, 36, 38, 39** and **37**, respectively) was also due to the strong γ -shielding effect of O-methyl group¹⁰ at C-3 being exerted on the former. C-2 in **32, 33** and **34** should not experience such effect but the appearance of C-2 in higher field even compared to similar carbons in **48, 25** and **26**, respectively, indicated the operation of some other shielding mechanism here. In **16, 17** and **18**, the C-2 methoxyl had an *ortho* carbon substituent and comparison of the carbon signals of these compounds with those of **48, 25** and **26**, respectively indicated that the substituent effects of C-2 methoxyl in **16-18** on *ortho* and *para* carbons (Table 3) were slightly less than expected. Furthermore, the effect on the *ortho* carbons (C-1 and C-3) was surprisingly somewhat similar.

Table 4 shows the effect of the addition of substituents in relation to the basic 1,2,3-trimethoxybenzene skeleton¹¹. The effect was somewhat additive when the substituent was free from steric involvement. Otherwise, when all the four substituents were on contiguous carbons the deviation was quite appreciable.

Experimental

The ¹³C-nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian Associates CFT-20 NMR spectrometer. The compounds were submitted to NDC and SFORD to establish the carbon shifts and the degree

TABLE 1—CARBON-13 NMR SHIFT (δ) OF THE TRIOXYGENATED BENZENE DERIVATIVES 1-20 AND 40-42

	1 ^a	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 ^a	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19 ^e	20 ^f	40 ^g	41 ^h	42 ^h
O-1	121.0	124.5	136.6	132.8	125.1	120.5	126.7	125.3	128.8	121.2	125.2	128.7	122.6	119.8	120.4	117.5	118.3	114.1	123.0 ^b	120.1	114.8	118.0	122.9
O-2	109.4	106.3	103.0	105.9	104.5	104.6	106.5	104.7	106.4	103.2	106.7	108.6	156.1	151.7	151.8	158.7	151.5	151.6	109.8	126.1 ^b	154.1	104.3	104.7
O-3	145.2	152.3	152.3	152.9	147.1	159.2	153.4	153.2	146.3	152.6	152.5	141.0	141.8	142.0	142.0	96.3	97.5	97.7	148.9	149.0	96.7	146.4	152.7
O-4	138.0	141.6	136.1	137.9	136.9	134.8	137.3	136.1	136.0	138.9	136.9	137.0	158.7	158.1	153.0	156.0	148.8	148.8	147.8	144.3	152.4	134.1	137.5
O-5	145.2	152.3	152.3	152.9	147.1	159.2	153.4	153.2	146.3	152.6	152.5	141.0	141.8	142.0	142.0	96.3	97.5	97.7	148.9	149.0	96.7	146.4	152.7
O-6	109.4	106.2	103.0	105.9	104.5	104.6	106.5	104.7	106.4	103.2	106.7	108.6	106.9	107.0	107.0	109.2	114.6	114.7	122.6 ^b	126.4 ^b	114.6	104.3	104.7
O-OCH ₃												128.4	124.7	124.5	56.2	56.3 ^b	56.4 ^b			61.7 ^c	56.3 ^b	55.3	55.3
O-OCH ₃	55.5	55.1	55.8	55.3	56.1	56.0	55.7	55.8				61.1 ^b	60.4	60.5	56.2	56.1 ^b	56.2 ^b			61.0 ^c	56.1 ^b	55.3	55.3
O-OCH ₃	60.1	59.9	60.1	59.8	60.7							55.4	55.7	55.8	56.2	55.8 ^b	55.9 ^b			60.6 ^c	55.9 ^b	55.3	55.3
O-OCH ₃	55.5	55.1	55.8	55.3	56.1	56.0	55.7	55.8	56.2	55.8	56.0					56.2	55.8 ^b				55.9 ^b	55.3	55.3
O-1'	166.9	165.9	63.8	33.9	22.6	23.1	41.1	23.1	41.0	22.4	23.1	41.1	187.8	35.4	35.0	187.6	34.7	34.7	85.0	32.3	141.5		
O-2'																					111.0		
COOCH ₃	51.4	51.4																			170.9		
-OCH ₃ -																					170.9		
O-1''							74.5	74.7			70.8	71.1									51.5		
O-2''6''							137.2	137.5			136.3	136.8											
O-3''5''							127.7 ^b	127.8 ^b			137.3	137.7											
O-4''							127.9 ^b	123.1 ^b			138	128.2 ^b											
							127.4	127.5			137.5	127.3											
											127.6												

a : In d_6 -acetone ; $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{d_6\text{-acetone}} + 29.2$ ppm.
 b,c : Assignments along a vertical column may be interchanged.
 d : In d_6 -DMSO ; $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{d_6\text{-DMSO}} + 39.6$ ppm.
 e : -CH₂O- resonated at δ 69.5 ppm.
 f : -CH₂O- and CH₂OH resonated at δ 64.9 and 55.4, respectively.
 g : -COOH resonated at δ 173.0 ppm.

TABLE 2—CARBON-13 NMR SHIFT (δ) OF THE BENZENE DERIVATIVE 21-39 AND 45-48

	21 ^a	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31 ^e	32 ^e	33 ^e	34 ^e	35	36	37 ^a	38 ^a	39	45	46	47	48 ^h
O-1	133.3	123.4	130.7	133.3	125.6	126.1	130.0	132.0	126.3	127.0	125.9	131.7	126.7	127.3	125.2	125.8	125.5	128.0	126.3	120.1	123.0	125.7	129.8
O-2	112.3	111.7	111.1	113.1	112.3	112.3	112.3	112.7	112.9	112.9	113.8	103.6	109.7	109.5	130.3	130.0	130.6	130.6	130.6	130.0	127.6	129.1	131.7
O-3	148.6	145.3	149.9 ^b	147.2 ^b	148.6	145.5	149.8	149.8	149.4	149.4	147.5	148.5	147.6	147.6	114.0	113.7	115.4	114.8	114.6	128.7	128.3	114.1	149.2
O-4	153.0	152.7	148.3 ^b	147.1 ^b	148.0	147.8	153.3	146.8	147.3	147.1	145.4	152.9	146.7	146.6	158.8	159.4	156.4	157.3	157.8	127.6	127.0	164.4	154.1
O-5	111.2	110.1 ^d	110.8 ^d	111.1 ^d	111.0 ^d	111.0 ^d	112.3 ^d	114.4 ^d	113.8 ^d	114.0 ^d	115.0 ^d	108.2 ^d	108.2 ^d	108.1 ^d	114.0	113.7	115.4	114.8	114.6	128.7	128.3	114.1	110.1 ^d
O-6	123.6 ^d	123.2 ^d	120.9 ^d	120.9 ^d	120.9 ^d	120.9 ^d	127.8 ^d	127.8 ^d	127.8 ^d	127.8 ^d	121.4 ^d	121.8 ^d	121.8 ^d	122.4 ^d	122.3 ^d								
O-OCH ₃	55.8 ^c	55.6	55.8 ^c	55.7	55.5	55.4	55.6	55.9	55.7	55.7	55.7	55.8											
O-OCH ₃	55.7 ^c	55.6	55.7 ^c	55.7	55.5	55.4	55.6	55.9	55.7	55.7	55.7	55.8											
O-1'	167.5	166.4	71.6	37.9	40.3	40.1	190.4	71.1	43.4	40.4	40.7	193.0	40.5	40.6	40.0	39.9	40.2	40.7	39.8	23.0	40.7	190.6	190.4
O-2'																							
COOCH ₃	51.5																						
OCH ₃																							
O-1''																							
O-2''6''																							
O-3''5''																							
O-4''																							

a : In d_6 -DMSO ; $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{d_6\text{-DMSO}} + 39.6$ ppm.
 b,c : Assignments interchangeable.
 d : Virtual coupling observed in the SFORD spectrum.
 e : -OCH₃O- resonated at δ 101.9, 100.9 and 100.8 in 32, 33 and 34 respectively.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF A METHOXY SUBSTITUENT (in ppm) ON AN AROMATIC RING

Compound studied	Reference compound	C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4	C-5	C-6
2	22	2.1	-5.5	4.0	-11.1	42.2	-17.0
3	23	5.9	-8.1	3.4	-12.4	41.5	-17.3
4	24	-0.5	-7.2	5.7	-9.2	41.8	-14.4
7	25	3.1	-5.8	4.6	-10.7	42.2	-14.8
9	29	2.6	-6.5	3.8	-11.3	39.4	-15.0
13	48	-7.2	47.4	-8.2	4.6	-3.2	-3.0
14	25	-5.8	39.4	-6.8	5.1	-4.0	3.4
15	26	-5.7	39.7	-6.5	5.2	-3.9	3.5
16	44	-12.3	32.3	-13.8	1.9	-5.5	0.5
17	25	-12.3	30.3	-13.5	0.8	-6.0	2.3
18	26	-12.0	30.6	-13.2	0.9	-5.7	2.6
25	35	0.4	-18.0	34.6	-10.8	-3.0	-8.7
26	36	0.3	-17.9	34.8	-10.6	-2.8	-9.0
29	38	-1.8	-17.7	34.6	-10.0	-1.0	-9.2
30	39	0.8	-17.1	34.8	-10.7	-0.6	-8.9
31	37	0.4	-16.8	32.1	-11.0	0.1	-8.8
35	46	-7.8	1.2	-14.3	31.8	-14.3	1.2

- 10 R¹=CH₂CN, R²=H
 11 R¹=CH₂CN, R²=CH₂Ph
 12 R¹=CH₂COOH, R²=CH₂Ph
 13 R=CHO
 14 R=CH₂COOH
 15 R=CH₂COOCH₃
 16 R=CHO
 17 R=CH₂COOH
 18 R=CH₂COOCH₃
 40 R=CH=CH-COOH

TABLE 4—EFFECTS OF SUBSTITUENTS IN RELATION TO 1,2,3-TRIMETHOXYBENZENE MOIETY

Substituents	C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4
COOCH ₃	1.6 (1.3) ^m	1.5 (-0.5)	-0.4 (-0.5)	4.1 (3.5)
CH ₂ OH	13.7 (12.3)	-1.7 (-1.4)	-0.4 (-1.4)	-1.4 (-1.4)
CH ₂ Br	9.9	1.2	0.2	0.4
CH ₂ CN	2.2	-0.2	0.1	-0.6
CH ₂ CN ¹	1.4	-1.1	0.0	-1.1
CH ₂ COOH	5.8	1.8	0.5	-0.2
CH ₂ COOH ¹	4.3	0.4	-0.4	-1.7
CH ₂ COOH ^{k,1}	15.1	-1.0	4.3	0.4

i: Substituent effects observed in 45 relative to benzene (δ 128.7).

j: Substituent effects observed in 46 relative to benzene.

k: Substituent effects observed in 14 relative to 42.

l: C-5 and C-6 in 14 suffered downfield shifts by 2.3 and 1.8 ppm, respectively.

m: Values in the parentheses from Ref. 8.

- 19 R¹=R²=H
 20 R¹=OCH₃, R²=CH₂OH
 21 R=COOH
 22 R=COOCH₃
 23 R=CH₂OH
 24 R=CH₂Br
 25 R=CH₂COOH
 26 R=CH₂COOCH₃
 48 R=CHO
 27 R=CHO
 28 R=CH₂OH
 29 R=CH₂COOCH₃
 30 R=CH₂COOCH₃

- 31 R=OCH₃
 37 R=H
 32 R=CHO
 33 R=CH₂COOH
 34 R=CH₂COOCH₃
 35 R¹=OCH₃, R²=CH₂COOH
 36 R¹=OCH₃, R²=CH₂COOCH₃
 38 R¹=OCH₃Ph, R²=CH₂COOH
 39 R¹=OCH₃Ph, R²=CH₂COOCH₃
 45 R¹=H, R²=CH₂CN
 46 R¹=H, R²=CH₂COOH
 47 R¹=OCH₃, R²=CHO

- 1 R¹=COOCH₃, R²=H
 2 R=COOCH₃
 3 R=CH₂OH
 6 R¹=CH₂CN, R²=CH₂
 41 R¹=H, R²=CH₂
 4 R=CH₂Br
 5 R=CH₂CN
 7 R=CH₂COOCH₃
 42 R=H
 8 R=CH₂CN
 9 R=CH₂COOH

of protonation. The spectra were recorded in 10 mm o.d. tubes using CDCl₃ (unless otherwise stated) as solvent as well as internal lock and internal standard. All solutions were ca 10-25% in concentration. The chemical shifts reported are in δ (ppm) downfield from TMS; $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9$ ppm. The spectra were run with sweep width 4000 Hz (4500 Hz in case of 43 and 44), pulse width 12 μ s (approximately 60° flip angle) and about 1-3 μ s delay between pulses.

Gallic acid afforded **2**¹² when refluxed with Me₂SO₄ (4.5 eq) and anhydrous Na₂CO₃ in dry acetone whereas stirring of gallic acid at room temperature with Me₂SO₄ (1 eq) and Na₂CO₃ in dry acetone furnished **1**¹⁸. LAH reduction (THF) of **2**, **22** and **27** gave **3**¹², **23**¹⁸ and **28**, respectively. **3** and **23** yielded **4**¹² and **24**¹⁴, respectively on treatment with PBr₃ and NEt₃ in CCl₄. **5** was obtained from **4** by the action of NaCN in DMSO at room temperature¹². **6** and **10** were obtained from **5** upon treatment with BBr₃ in CH₂Cl₂ at ice cold temperature¹⁴. **6**, **10** and **37**¹⁸ were converted to **8**¹⁴, **11**¹⁴ and **38**¹⁸, respectively by refluxing with benzyl chloride, K₂CO₃ and catalytic amount of KI in EtOH. **5**, **8** and **11** were hydrolysed under basic condition to **7**¹², **9**¹⁴ and **12**¹⁴, respectively while **19**¹² and **20**¹² were obtained from **25** and **7**, respectively following the procedure of Nagata *et al*¹⁵. **14**¹⁴, **17**¹⁴, **25**¹⁸, **29**¹⁴, **33**¹⁸ and **35**¹⁸ were obtained by basic hydrolysis of **15**, **18**, **26**, **30**, **34** and **36**, respectively which were obtained from **13**, **16**, **48**, **27**, **32** and **47**, respectively through the formation of azalactone derivatives¹⁸. Oxidation of veratraldehyde using alkaline KMnO₄ afforded **21**¹⁸. **21** and **37** on methylation with Me₂SO₄ and K₂CO₃ furnished **22**¹⁸ and **36**¹⁸, respectively. Hydrogenolysis of **29** in presence of 10% Pd-C in ethanol afforded **31**¹⁸. Asarylaldehyde (**16**) was isolated from *Acorus calamus*⁶. **40** was obtained by the condensation of **16** with malonic acid in presence of pyridine and piperidine¹⁴. All the compounds were purified either by distillation under reduced pressure or by chromatography over silica gel or alumina and the identity of the compounds were established from their spectral data.

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References

1. J. BANERJI, R. N. REJ and A. CHATTERJEE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 698.
2. A. PATRA, A. K. MITRA, A. GHOSH and P. K. MUKHOPADHYAY, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1981, **16**, 65.
3. A. K. MITRA, A. PATRA and A. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17B**, 885.
4. A. PATRA and A. K. MITRA, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1981, **17**, 222.
5. A. PATRA, A. K. MITRA, A. BHATTACHARYYA and N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1982, **18**, 241.
6. A. PATRA and A. K. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17B**, 412.
7. A. PATRA and A. K. MITRA, *J. Natural Products (Lloydia)*, 1981, **44**, 668.
8. J. B. STOTHERS, "Carbon-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1972, p. 197.
9. G. O. LEVY and G. L. NELSON, "Carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy for Organic Chemists", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972, p. 81.
10. A. F. ERASMUSON, R. J. FERRIER, N. C. FRANCA, H. E. GOTTLIEB and E. WENKERT, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin I*, 1977, 492.
11. E. WENKERT, H. E. GOTTLIEB, O. R. GOTTLIEB, M. O. DA S. PERIRA and M. D. FORMIGA, *Phytochem.*, 1976, **15**, 1547.
12. A. PATRA, P. K. MUKHOPADHYAY and G. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, **21B**, 173.
13. J. R. A. POLLOCK and R. STEVENS (Eds.), "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 4th Edn., Eyre & Spottiswoode, London, 1965.
14. A. PATRA and P. K. MUKHOPADHYAY, unpublished results.
15. W. NAGATA, H. ITAZAKI, K. OKADA, T. WAKABAYASHI, K. SHIBATA and H. TOKUTAKE, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1975, **23**, 2867.
16. E. C. HORNING (Ed.), "Organic Syntheses", Coll. Vol. 3, John Wiley, New York, 1943, p. 343.